

**APPROPRIATE ENERGY MIX TO FACILITATE RURAL INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA**

Obi, P. I*. Ezeonye, C. S. and Amako, A. E.

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

Email: patndyobi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the appropriate energy mix to facilitate rural industrial development and economic growth in Nigeria. The study discusses the national energy policies, plans and programmes, its sustainable energy for all targets and its on-grid and off-grid energy mix demographic analysis including its percentage of population with access to energy. The results show that although Nigeria numerous renewable power project/plans still ongoing implementation, fossil fuel and hydropower are the only two sources currently in its energy mix. The results of the study also displayed a poor percentage of rural population with access to energy and rural electrification rate of 25.5 % and 55.6% respectively. The study concluded stating that the suitable energy mix in the rural area that would rapidly increase its development was labelled as the use of off-grid solution and stand-alone solar homes solutions, as this would increase their rural electrification and industrial development which will in turn contribute immensely to Nigeria's economic growth.

Keywords: Energy Mix, Off-Grid Solar Solution, Photovoltaic (PV), Rural Electrification, Total Primary Energy Consumption (TPEC).

INTRODUCTION

Energy mix is the generation of secondary energy such as electricity for direct use from a group of primary energy sources such as renewable and non-renewable (Planete, 2015). This involves the combination of renewable and non-renewable energy, that is, combination of fossil fuels (oil and natural gas) and nuclear energy with other renewable energies for generating power for residential and industrial consumption especially for rural industrial development. Energy mix in Nigeria is currently dominated by fossil fuels especially natural gas hence there is need to incorporate renewable energy sources in Nigeria energy mix for improvement in electrical energy needed for the country and to generate adequate electricity for rural industrial development (Ahuja and Tatsutani, 2009; Nweke, 2016; Ariyo *et al.*, 2018).

RESOURCES FOR ENERGY GENERATION IN NIGERIA

The resources available for energy generation in Nigeria is broadly classified into renewable and non-renewable energy resources. The renewable energy resources available for energy generation in Nigeria include wind, sun, hot springs, rivers, tides, plants and biomass. Due to climate change and global warming, there is need to incorporate more renewable energy sources in Nigeria's energy mix due to its environmental friendly and its' being clean energy. This will help in eliminating some problems associated with only non-renewable energy mix. Despite the abundance of rivers and dams in different part of the country which is the major resource of hydro energy, Nigeria is yet to fully harness the enormous potential of these waters. With over 280 potential sites with a combined capacity of about 4,000 MW for small hydro- power (SHP) development, only a few pilot projects have been initiated leaving the substantial part unexploited. Only rivers Niger and Benue and their tributaries form the base of the Nigerian river system with potential for large-scale hydropower (LSP) development capable of generating more than 100 MW of electricity (RERID, 2003; Utazi, 2014). In the solar section, Nigeria's annual average solar radiation ranges from 3.5 KWh/m²/day in the coast region to 7 KWh/m²/day in northern region. This implies that in a day, the annual average hours

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of sun varies from 4 hours in the south to 9 hours in the north. Since solar is eco-friendly, it is vital for rural industrial development and the power generated from solar systems can be fed into national grid and this in turn helps in total power supplied to national grid (Uzoma *et al.*, 2012). In wind energy generation, it uses airflow to generate electricity. Due to insufficient power in rural areas because of low energy generation, there is need to augment wind energy in Nigeria's energy mix for maximizing rural industrial production. Nigeria has good wind resources in most part of the country. Though wind speeds in the southern states are low, they can be used for standalone power generating systems for rural electrification especially those that are not connected to the national grid. The northern states with mean wind speeds of 4 to 8 m/s can be effectively connected to national grid for energy mix improvement. Due to inadequate funding by government in the areas of wind energy, this led to very little or non-existence of wind energy in the country. Therefore, government needs to develop a framework and provide more funds for the development of wind energy technology (Owoeye, 2017). In bio energy generation, the available resources in Nigeria are wood, forage grasses and shrubs, charcoal, animal dung, agricultural and forestry residue, municipal and industrial waste, and aquatic biomass. It offers the advantages of inexpensive, nearly unlimited availability of resources and can be used without essential damage to the environment. In 1990, Nigeria's total potential in biomass, consisting of wood residues, agricultural waste and animal dung, was estimated to be 1.2 PJ, while in 2005, research revealed that bio energy reserves/potential in the country stood at: animal dung, 61 million tons per year; fuel wood 13,071,464 ha; crop residues, 83 million tons. Due to biomass production being inherently rural, this will offer the prospect for improved energy generation in the rural area hence rural industrial development and subsequently country's economic growth. Also, the growing demand for bio resources and the resulting rise in agricultural commodity prices can present an opportunity for promoting agricultural growth and rural development in Nigeria (Masera and Faaij, 2014; Sokan-Adeaga and Ana, 2015).

The non-renewable energy resources available for energy generation in Nigeria include crude oil, natural gas, coal, and tar sand. Among these, the major resources for energy generation in the country are crude oil and natural gas which are the most developed source of fossil energy in the country. Nigeria boasts of the world's sixth largest reserve of crude oil. It has an estimated oil reserve of 38 billion barrels. It also has the largest natural gas reserves in Africa, but the sector is still underdeveloped as most of the gas is presently flared, despite a fine per 1000 cf of gas flared imposed by the Nigerian Government in the 1980s. It is increasingly an important gas province with proven reserves of nearly 5000 billion m³. The crude oil and gas reserves are mainly explored and located along the Niger Delta region, Gulf of Guinea, Bight of Bonny and offshore in Bight of Benin. Coal reserves an estimation of 3 billion tons while tar sand which is majorly derived from bitumen, used for road construction reserves an estimated 31 billion barrels of oil equivalent. In Nigeria, Coal was once in high local demand in the colonial period for the steam locomotives and today is slightly used in local coal producing states as a means of cooking. Natural gas is a cleaner and environmentally safer source of energy than oil; it is potentially exploitable and will contribute significantly to economic and rural industrial development of Nigeria. With the penetration of energy from coal and tar sand in the country's energy mix the total energy supplied to the national grid will improve and thereby contributing significantly to its energy demands for sustainable economic growth and rural industrial development (Oyedepo, 2012; Uzoma *et al.*, 2012; Oyedepo, 2013; Nweke, 2016).

ENERGY UTILIZATION AND CONSUMPTION IN NIGERIA

Nigeria's policy on energy utilization for industries, agriculture, transport and household is that there shall be adequate and reliable supply of energy mix to all these sectors at economic rate for industrial, economic and social activities of the country. The major areas of energy consumption and utilization in Nigeria are transportation and conversion of energy resources to electricity for household, commercial, agricultural, and industrial applications. According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA, 2014) and International Energy Agency (IEA 2014), traditional solid biomass and waste dominated Nigeria's Total Primary Energy Consumption (TPEC). The reports also showed

that the total primary energy supply for Nigeria in 2014 was 127,142 ktoe as against 69810 ktoe in 1990. The primary energy supply mix includes 85.5% of biofuels and waste, 11.3% natural gas, 2.8% crude oil and 0.4% hydro respectively. The largest source of primary energy supply in Nigeria has been biofuels and waste with fuel wood being the major primary source of biofuel (Emodi, 2016). In terms of consumption, biofuel and waste are the highest fuel consumed and the residential sector has the highest consumption rate. The residential sector utilizes energy for cooking, heating, lighting and it depends highly on fuel wood. It is readily available; this is why it utilized by over 60% of the population (Uzoma *et al.*, 2012). The energy consumption mix is poor, it shows that we have not developed our energy sector because a large percent of the population still resorts to fuel wood. The energy consumption mix is highly imbalanced due to the availability of biomass resources. According to (Akorede *et al.*, 2017), as of 2011, per capita electric energy consumption in Nigeria for an average household of 5 was 149 kWh per annum.

Coal was actually the prevalent energy resource until the discovery of petroleum. Owing to the fact that coal mines were shut down during the Nigerian civil war in 1967, many coal users switched to more readily available fuel, such as petroleum products. As in 1970, the energy and economic planners excluded coal in the context of their developmental plans, thus creating an imbalance in the energy mix of the country. However, coal is expected to supply about 25 percent of all energy consumption over the next three decades. The total installed capacity of Nigeria's major generating stations is about 5,000 MW, which come from three hydropower plants at Jebba, Kainji, and Shiroro, and two gas thermal plants at Afam and Sapele. However, available data have shown that the current utilization of energy from these plants is about 40 percent of their installed capacities. The rapid growth in demand for energy (electricity), which stands at about 17 percent per annum, coupled with the problems associated with the distribution, has not contributed to resolving the problem of under-utilization of energy resources in Nigeria. It has been revealed that Nigeria can be referred to as an energy state due to its abundance but unutilized energy resources. The use of the potential solar energy in the country has been limited by unavailability of solar appliances, e.g. heaters, cookers, refrigerators, on a commercial basis. The development of indigenous and efficient solar appliances is still at an early stage and should be accelerated for long-term integration into the energy mix of Nigeria. This situation also applies to that of other renewable energy resources like wind, nuclear, and biomass. They are yet to be fully utilized despite the fact that they abound in the nation. Incorporating their development into long-term energy mix plan of Nigeria is therefore necessary for solving the problem of inadequate energy supply in the country which will improve industrialization especially in the rural areas (Dosunmu and Omayone, 2003; Ubogu, 2015; Oluwatoni, 2017; Falobi, 2019).

Several scientists and researchers have carried out work on energy mix for sustainable industrial development. The role of energy mix in sustainable development of Nigeria was presented by Uzoma *et al.*, (2012). Their results showed that existing energy mix has little significant influence on sustainable development. They suggested that integrating exploitable energy sources such as renewables would promote stability in energy supply and sustainable development. The pattern of energy use in Nigeria and a case for the implementation of an energy efficiency policy as a possible strategy to address the nation's energy crisis was reviewed by Oyedepo, (2013). His study explores the role of industrial energy use in sustainable development in Nigeria and the potential sources to increase energy efficiency in industrial sector. Utazi, (2014) adopted a literature survey of reports and publications of various private and government institution in discussing the need for robust energy mix in tackling the epileptic electricity supply in Nigeria. He discussed alternative energy resources – hydro, solar, wind, biomass, coal and nuclear should be harnessed to reduce the country's reliance on gas and oil power plants. The prospects of tar sand in Nigeria energy mix was presented by Nweke, (2016). He showed that increasing volume of cheaper heavy oil in the supply mix has provided an incentive for refiners to upgrade their equipment to process the poorer-quality heavier crude occurring in tar sand. Ariyo *et al.*, (2018) used Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewable (HOMER) to present optimization of hybrid energy mix for rural electrification in

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Nigeria. Their results showed that photovoltaic/diesel/battery came up as the most financially viable and sustainable solution to hybrid energy mix in Nigeria. The importance of energy access to development and particularly, modern energy services to rural development in Nigeria was discussed by Uzoma and Amadi, (2019). They showed that modern energy access will promote holistic, meaningful rural development in Nigeria.

THE NIGERIA ENERGY MIX

Recall that according to IEA (2014), the primary energy supply mix includes 85.5% biofuels and waste, 11.3% natural gas, 2.8% crude oil and 0.4% hydro respectively.

In relation to the electricity sector in Nigeria, individuals are allowed to install and run an off-grid power generator, however with a capacity below 1 MW; all forms of generation above this must obtain a generation license from NERC. In 2012, NERC signed two regulations- the Independent Electricity Distribution Network (IEDN) and Embedded Generation. The IEDN allows for communities, local and state government to invest in electricity distribution networks in areas with little or no access to the grid, bad distribution network or poorly serviced areas. All these in a bid to improve energy-mix in Nigeria.

NATIONAL ENERGY POLICIES, PLANS AND PROGRAMMES

There are more than thirty (30) draft policy documents which have been formulated by various actors in the energy sector. However, only very few of these policy documents have been approved and enforced to date, these include National Electric Power Policy (NEPP), 2002; National Energy Policy (NEP), 2003; Rural Electrification Policy Paper, 2009; Roadmap for Power Sector Reforms, 2010. The Federal Government of Nigeria in May 2015 approved the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) as well as the National Determined Contribution (NDC), 2015 which established Nigeria's commitment to greenhouse gas emission. NREEEP seeks to increase the share of on-grid renewable energy in the total electricity supply from its current 1.3% in 2015 to 16% in 2030. However, with the completion and validation of NREAP 2016, this target is now reviewed to 30% renewable energy by 2030.

A. Nigerian's SE4All Targets For 2030

The Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL) Action Agenda of Nigeria is a national implementation tool for the emerging Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) on energy (SDG No. 7) with aims of:

I. Energy Access:

- To increase electricity access from the current aggregate level of 40% (urban=65%, and rural=28%) in 2015 to 75% (urban= 90%, and rural= 60%) by 2020
- By 2030, the population share living without electricity supplies will drop from the current 60% in 2015 of the total population down to about 10%.
- By 2025 and 2030, nuclear energy is expected to contribute about 2.5% and 4% to available electricity mix.
- The electricity generation will increase from the present grid supply of 5687 MW in 2016 to at least 32,000 MW by 2030.

II. Energy Efficiency

By the end of 2015, efficient lighting (at least 5 times more efficient than incandescent lamps) will be used by 20% of the households, 40% by 2020 and almost 100% by 2030.

B. Nigeria's Targets for Energy Mix

Electricity will be a major contributor to the overall supply of modern energy in the country with a projected increase in the total capacity 23.5 GW and 45 GW in 2020, 2030 respectively. As shown in Figure 1, electricity supply will come from on-grid, off-grid and self-generation. On-grid supply will increase from current level of 26% (2016) to 48% and 70% in 2020 and 2030 respectively, while the use of self-generated power shall decline from the present level of 74% to about 49% and 18%

in 2020 and 2030 respectively. Figure 1 also highlighted the overall supply from off-grid systems (mini-grid and solar home systems) to reach 3% and 12% in 2020 and 2030 respectively (GIZ, 2015).

Table 1: Targets Contribution of Electricity Supply: % On-grid, Off-grid and Self Generation as of 2016 and by 2020 and 2030.

	As At 2016	Nigeria's Target at 2020	Nigeria's Target at 2030
On-Grid (Fossil fuel + Renewable) in GW	5.687	10.5	30
Off-Grid in GW	0.2	0.54	8
Self-generated (stand-alone) in GW	15.86	10.5	5

[Source: GIZ, 2015]

Figure 1: Targets Contribution of Electricity Supply: % On-grid, Off-grid and Self Generation as of 2016 and by 2020 and 2030

RENEWABLE ENERGY INTEGRATION IN NIGERIA

Assessing the status of renewable energy integration in Nigeria can be quite difficult as there are no official reports on this, though there are unofficial knowledge of stand-alone renewable energy installations all over the country. There are many projects written in policy documents and under the renewable energy programme, yet their current status could not be ascertained in the course of this study due to the lack of comprehensive database (Oluwatoni, 2017). There is however evidently slow integration of renewable energy into the energy mix despite its abundance in the nation.

- A. Solar Energy technology and utilization:** in Nigeria are either stand-alone mini-grid or off-grid light application as there are currently no off-grid hybrid or grid connected solar systems. Currently, most of the solar PV installations in Nigeria are from private individuals and investors. Therefore, there is no official report or database that gives the exact number of private solar installations.
- B. Wind energy technology:** the nation currently has two existing wind electricity technology that are functioning, these include 1 kW Benin energy research centre Edo State, rehabilitated wind power pump at Kadawa village in Kano State, 5 kWp capacity located at Sayya Gidan-Gada and 0.75 kWp located at Danjawa village both in Sokoto State (Aliyu *et al.*, 2015).
- C. Biomass Energy (Biofuel and Fuel wood):** Biomass accounts for a high percentage in the Nigeria's energy mix. However, fuel wood is not used efficiently or in a renewable way, hence the focus in Nigeria is on improving efficiency in fuel wood usage and also attempting to integrate biofuel into the Nigeria's energy mix.
- D. Hydropower:** Hydropower is the largest commercially exploited renewable energy source in Nigeria. The nation generates more from LHPs. The government, nevertheless, is making attempts to construct both LHP and SHP plants. Hydropower potential in Nigeria is enormous yet its current LHP integration is about 14% of its potential while its SHP integration is 19% of its current potential. This is too low given the fact that 64,000 MW can be generated if only 1% of the current potential can be harnessed.

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NIGERIA’S ENERGY DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

A. Nigeria’s Rural population

This refers to people living in rural areas as defined by national statistical offices. It is calculated as the difference between total population and urban population. Aggregation of urban and rural population may not add up to total population because of different country coverage. For the 70% of the world's poor who live in rural areas, agriculture is the main source of income and employment. But depletion and degradation of land and water pose serious challenges to producing enough food and other agricultural products to sustain livelihoods here and meet the needs of urban populations (Oluwatoni, 2017). Figure 2 shows an increase in rural population of about 9.44 million people per year, whereas Figure 3 shows a decline in rural growth rate and % of rural population of about 0.092 % and 4.75 % over the eleven years in review. This was mainly attributed to migration to the urban areas.

Table 2. Rural population, annual growth % and % of total Population

YEAR	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Rural population	8.96E+07	9.06E+07	9.16E+07	9.26E+07	9.35E+07	9.45E+07	9.54E+07	9.64E+07	9.73E+07	9.82E+07	9.90E+07
Rural population growth (annual %)	1.11	1.1	1.09	1.07	1.05	1.02	0.99	0.97	0.94	0.91	0.89
Rural population (% of total population)	56.52	55.634	54.754	53.882	53.018	52.162	51.317	50.481	49.656	48.843	48.042

[Source: <http://www.worldbank.org/>]

Rural Population In Nigeria

Figure 2: Rural population Growth of Nigeria from 2010-2019.

Figure 3: Rural population annual growth % and % of total Nigeria’s population from 2010-2020.

Nigeria's Percentage Access to Energy

This is the percentage of population with access to energy in the form of electricity. The electrification data are collected from industry, national surveys, and international sources (SE4ALL, 2016). Also the rural percentage with access to electricity, is the percentage of rural population with access to electricity via the Nations Grid system. Figure 4 shows percentage of Nigerians with access to electricity and percentage of rural population with access to electricity – this indicates a stagnated development increment rate of about 4.96% per year over the period in review and a percentage rural access to electricity development rate of about 2.55 % over the eleven year period in review indicating lack of commitment improving the nations access and rural access to energy. In Figure 5, the Access to energy of similar developing African nations (Arab Republic of Egypt, Kenya and South Africa) was compared with Nigeria for 2019 and it showed that the percentage of rural population with access to energy from the grid was higher in the three other similar nations than in Nigeria which had a lowly 25.5 %.

Table 3a: Access to Energy

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Access to electricity (% of population)	48.0	55.9	53.2	55.6	54.4	52.5	59.3	54.4	56.5	55.4
Access to electricity, rural (% of rural population)	23.54	31.02	27.61	31.63	28.10	25.90	33.97	22.62	30.95	25.55

[Source: <http://www.worldbank.org/>]

Table 3b: Access to Energy of similar Developing African Nations in 2019

		Arab Republic of Egypt	Kenya	<i>Nigeria</i>	South Africa
2019	% of Population	100	69.8	<i>55.4</i>	85
	% of Rural Population	100	61.7	<i>25.5</i>	79.2

[Source: <http://www.worldbank.org/>]

Figure 4: Access to electricity (% of population) and % of rural population.

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Figure 5: Access to Energy of Similar African Countries.

C. Nigeria’s Existing On-Grid Energy Mix

Rural Electrification: The electrification rate calculated by the World Bank for 2011 was 48.0% (World Bank Group). According to UNESCO and IEA, the electrification rate in Nigeria in 2009 was 50.6 %, while triangulation of available data suggests that total grid access to electricity hovers around 35–40% (NIAF, 2014). The differing data show the difficulty to define and calculate the access rate, but the tendency is in the same range. However, it shows that many more households might be technically connected to the grid. However, the data reflect the considerable extent of self-provision and backup generation of electricity in Nigeria, in form of large generators and solar stand-alone systems in industry and by many big commercial establishments. At the other end of the spectrum there are the ubiquitous small portable generators and Inverters used by households and shops to supply electricity at very high unit cost. Figure 6 displays the household electrification rate by federal states while Figure 7 shows the electrification rate by geopolitical zone according to this data set (National Bureau of Statistics, 2014). It could be seen that the North East has the least electrification rate of 27 % partly due to the on-going crises and their enormous land mass and mainly rural nature. It has to be kept in mind that access to electricity and grid coverage are two different issues in Nigeria.

Figure 6: Household Electrification Rate by federal states (National Bureau of Statistics, 2014)

Figure 7: Electrification Rate by Geopolitical Zone (National Bureau of Statistics, 2014)

When compared to other African developing countries with similar economies, population and political demographics such as South Africa, Arab Republic of Egypt and Kenya. It can be seen in Figure 8, that Kenya is the highest with about 74.8 % renewable electricity output on-grid (i.e. % of the total electricity output) while Nigeria has a value of 20.02% which are mainly as a result of hydropower generated in the two countries. This renewable electricity is the share of electricity generated by renewable power plants in total electricity generated by all types of plants. Figure 9 showed that other African countries in context (South Africa, Arab Republic of Egypt and Kenya) generate electricity via other means especially through solar power and wind power unlike Nigeria that has no other renewable connected to the grid. Hence no electricity production from other renewable sources.

Table 5: Renewable electricity output (% of country total electricity output)

	Egypt, Arab Republic	Kenya	Nigeria	South Africa
2010	10.05	69.07	24.40	0.95
2011	9.33	66.87	21.76	0.92
2012	8.88	74.78	19.71	0.60
2013	8.88	69.29	18.44	0.61
2014	8.87	81.49	17.59	1.29
2015	8.26	87.51	18.20	2.26

[Source: <http://www.worldbank.org/>]

Table 6: Electricity Production from other Renewable Sources, Excluding Hydroelectric (Kwh)

Electricity Production From Renewable Sources, Excluding Hydroelectric (Kwh)				
	Egypt, Arab Republic	Kenya	Nigeria	South Africa
2010	1.70E+09	1.68E+09	0	3.2E+08
2011	1.75E+09	1.735E+09	0	3.27E+08
2012	1.50E+09	1.808E+09	0	3.32E+08
2013	1.57E+09	2.205E+09	0	3.83E+08
2014	1.69E+09	4.234E+09	0	2.25E+09
2015	1.60E+09	4.659E+09	0	4.76E+09

[Source: <http://www.worldbank.org/>]

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Figure 8: Renewable electricity output (% of country total electricity output)

Figure 9: Electricity production from other renewable sources excluding hydroelectricity

D. Nigeria's Off-Grid Energy Mix

Reporting current off-grid capacity and generation is undoubtedly challenging. Even when generators of 1 MW or more must be registered with the Federal Ministry of Power (FMP) only limited actual data is available. There is an estimated installed capacity of 8–14 GW off-grid diesel and gasoline generators the majority of which is installed by individual people in urban areas to cover power outages from the national grid. Households in rural areas usually cannot afford to buy and operate generator sets. The potential of renewable energy mix in Nigeria as prepared by the Energy Commission of Nigeria is shown in Table 7. Table 8 shows the existing NERC licenses issued on renewable energy in Nigeria while Table 9 shows the Hydropower development plan by the Federal Ministry of Power as of 2014.

Table 7: Potentials for Renewable Energy Mix

Resource	Potential	Current Utilization and further remarks
Large Hydropower	11,250 MW	1,900 MW exploited
Small Hydropower	3,500 MW	64.2 MW exploited
Solar	4.0 kWh/m²/day – 6.5 kWh/m²/day	15 MW dispersed solar PV installations. (estimated)
Wind	2–4m/s @ 10m height mainland	Electronic wind information system (WIS) available;
Biomass (non-fossil organic matter)	Municipal waste	18.5 million tonnes produced in 2005 and now estimated at 0.5kg/capita/day
	Fuel wood	43.4 million tonnes/yr. fuel wood consumption
	Animal waste	245 million assorted animals in 2001
	Agricultural residues	91.4 million tonnes/yr. produced
	Energy crops	28.2 million hectares of arable land; 8.5% cultivated

[Source: ECN; 2014]

Table 8: NERC Licensees, Renewable Energy

Name of Licensee	Capacity (MW)	Fuel Type	State	Geopolitical Zone
JAP Energy Limited	504	Biomass	Lagos	South-West
Premier Energy Limited	50	Hydrogen fuel cell	Adamawa	North-East
Rook Solar Investment Limited	50	Solar	Osun	South-West
Quaint Global Nigeria Limited	50	Solar	Kaduna	North-West
Nigeria Solar Capital Partners	100	Solar	Bauchi	North-East
Anjeed Kafanchan Solar Limited	10	Solar	Kaduna	North-West
Lloyd and Baxter LP	50	Solar	Abuja	North-Central
KVK Power Pvt Limited	50	Solar	Sokoto	North-West
Pan African Solar	54	Solar	Katsina	North-West
Mabon Limited	39	Hydro	Gombe	North-East
JBS Wind	100	Wind	Plateau	North-Central

[Source: www.power.gov.ng/]

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Table 9: Hydropower Development by FMP, 2014

No.	Power Station	MW	Zone	Status
1	Zungeru project - Niger State	700	North Central	financing secured
2	Mambilla Project - Taraba State	3,050	North East	under development
3	Gurara II Project - Niger State	360	North Central	under development
4	Gurara I Project - Niger State	30	North Central	under development
5	Itisi Project - Kaduna State	40	North West	under development
6	Kashimbilla Project - Taraba State	40	North East	under development

[Source: www.power.gov.ng/]

Rural Electrification Market and Potentials: The market potential for rural electrification is huge, since the current electrification rate in Nigeria is just around 50 %. It could be worth pursuing small solar PV installations, mini or small hydropower plants and larger hybrid systems to provide electricity to rural communities. Even small, decentralized biogas projects offer vast potential. Off-grid generation is undoubtedly challenging. However, the Rural Electrification Agency (REA) has about 600 projects ongoing, mainly in the field of solar energy and energy efficiency. Other small projects are being pursued by various institutions and companies. These energy mix if integrated fully, can increase Nigeria's current energy supply through renewable energy by about 60,000 MW or 60 GW with no substantial increase in environmental pollution.

Challenges of Rural Energy Mix Implementation in Nigeria

- Lack of indigenous components and technical know-how
- Project implementation/corruption
- Change of government
- Lack of policy implementation
- Lack of standardization
- Inadequate incentives for renewable energy development
- Lack of adequate funds.

CONCLUSION

The energy sector is the backbone of the nation's economy. It significantly lacks behind, with only fossil fuel and hydropower been currently used - this forms the Nigeria Energy Mix structure.

This study established in the findings that, Nigeria has abundant conventional and renewable energy resources but has a deteriorating state of energy mix and security. The nation has mainly focused on exploitation of its conventional source of energy, mainly fossil fuels over the years and its' renewable energy potentials have been minimally exploited. Failure to diversify the sources of energy and it's already energy mix structure led to increase in demand for energy. Lack of new energy infrastructures and lack of proper maintenance of existing infrastructures are major reason for poor energy mix especially in rural areas thus limiting their development.

It has been shown that, there has been very minimal practical steps taken by the government. Although, the current government is making attempts, however, this can be attributed to the increased awareness of renewable energy at the global level. Energy mix - if integrated fully, can increase Nigeria's current energy supply through renewable energy by about 60,000 MW or 60 GW with no substantial increase in environmental pollution.

The rural electrification sector still awaits the approval of the Rural Electrification Strategy and Plan. Operationalization of the Rural Electrification Fund is as important as a coherent planning and regulatory framework in order to promote investments and streamline the actions of federal, state and private actors towards a mass roll-out of electrification projects across the country.

A suitable energy mix in the rural area would rapidly increase its development through the use of off-grid solution and stand-alone solar homes solutions. This would increase the rural electrification and development. Energy efficiency still needs to be embraced by stakeholders and the population at large as a cost-effective tool to save electricity and to improve the reliability of the power system. Conducting this study has also shown that the availability of data is a major challenge. However, it is hoped that this publication alleviates this situation to a certain extent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends that the Nigerian government needs to take more active and practical steps in improving the integration of renewable energy into its current energy mix especially for rural areas that are off- the grid or have poor electricity supply. Most importantly, if these current renewable energy projects are fully executed and integrated in rural areas, there will be improvements in the nation's state of energy mix and security. This will improve economic growth and development; thereby leading to increased investment in rural economy development, reduced migration to urban cities.

Also, it is recommended, to improve its energy mix in rural area, the government needs to focus more on immediate cost effective off-grid solutions and stand-alone solar home system (SHS) for the rural populace while it speeds up its maintenance plans on the existing structures and On-grid connection of these communities.

Similarly, by providing more incentives like cash rebate to encourage investments from individuals, the private sector and international organizations.

Furthermore, this study also recommends that the government should also provide adequate information on the benefits of renewable energy and appropriate energy mix for rural development with the aim of increasing awareness especially among the rural populace and focus on immediate cheaper off-grid solutions.

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APPENDIX

Table A1: Household Electrification Rate by State in Percentage

State of Residence	% Have Electricity	% No Electricity	% Missing	Number of households surveyed
North Central	48.7	51.2	0.1	5,942
FCT-Abuja	77.7	22.0	0.3	361
Benue	22.1	77.9	0.0	1,365
Kogi	62.9	37.1	0.0	876
Kwara	90.6	9.1	0.3	617
Nasarawa	33.2	66.5	0.3	550
Niger	51.7	48.2	0.1	1,504
Plateau	36.3	63.7	0.0	669
North East	29.3	70.4	0.3	5,115
Adamawa	37.6	62.2	0.2	726
Bauchi	29.3	70.3	0.4	932
Borno	33.0	66.5	0.5	1,560
Gombe	48.1	51.8	0.1	464
Taraba	10.9	88.8	0.3	634
Yobe	18.1	81.7	0.2	799
North West	42.2	57.7	0.1	9,992
Jigawa	26.0	74.0	0.0	1,152
Kaduna	53.5	46.2	0.3	1,915
Kano	52.1	47.9	0.0	2,606
Katsina	31.3	68.5	0.2	1,257
Kebbi	44.4	55.6	0.0	1,069
Sokoto	38.9	60.9	0.2	898
Zamfara	29.1	70.6	0.3	1,096
South East	66.4	33.6	0.0	4,687
Abia	81.7	18.3	0.0	644
Anambra	88.1	11.8	0.1	1,050
Ebonyi	39.2	60.7	0.1	978
Enugu	55.4	44.6	0.0	920
Imo	69.9	30.1	0.0	1,096
South South	68.3	31.3	0.4	5,239
Akwa Ibom	68.0	31.8	0.2	892
Bayelsa	52.5	47.3	0.2	322
Cross River	57.4	41.4	1.2	848
Delta	78.3	21.6	0.1	946
Edo	82.4	17.5	0.1	702
Rivers	65.1	34.5	0.4	1,529
South West	81.1	18.8	0.1	7,546
Ekiti	92.7	7.3	0.0	376
Lagos	99.3	0.5	0.2	2,240
Ogun	72.0	27.9	0.1	1,355
Ondo	66.3	33.7	0.0	920
Osun	89.4	10.6	0.0	853
Oyo	66.6	33.3	0.1	1,802
Total	55.6	44.2	0.2	38,522